

Exploring the Impact of Post-Treatment Complications in Cervical Cancer

Survivors: A Global Perspective

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this study is to explore post-treatment complications across regions, treatment types, and time after treatment.

Methods: We performed a comprehensive literature search via electronic database (Google Scholar, and PubMed) with the use of a combination of the following keywords: cervical cancer survivors, posttreatment complications, long-term effects, and survivorship. The findings considered in the present review were the study design, the number of patients included in each study, the information about the difficulties after treatment, and the main findings. All studies were published between 2008–2024.

Results: Total 17 studies were reviewed. Sexual dysfunction, bladder and bowel difficulties, chronic pain, and lymphedema were the most common post-treatment effects. Anxiety, depression, and body image issues were frequently observed, with survivors in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) suffering significant emotional and financial difficulties. Surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy have been linked to both short-term (infections, fatigue) and long-term (sexual dysfunction, chronic pain) consequences. Survivors in high-income countries (HICs) had better long-term outcomes than those in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Conclusion: Sexual dysfunction is one of the major challenges that cervical cancer survivors face, which persists long after curative treatment. Survivors in low- and middle-income countries had

worse outcomes, highlighting the urgent need for better survivorship care, emotional support, and treatment access globally.

Keywords: cervical cancer survivors; post-treatment complications; quality of life; short- and long-term effect.

1. Introduction

Cervical cancer caused 660,000 new cases and 350,000 deaths in 2022 (1), making it the 4th most frequent disease in women and it is a major public health problem globally (1–4). Persistent infection with high-risk human papillomavirus (HPV) subtypes is the primary cause (5,6), causing up to 99.7% of cases (7). While largely preventable with HPV vaccination and early detection, it remains a leading cause of death in low- and middle-income countries because of limited opportunities for screening and treatment (5,8). Surgery, radiation, and chemotherapy treatment have improved the overall survival of cervical cancer (2,9). However, long-term quality of life has been affected by treatment related side effects, including gastrointestinal, sexual, neurological, and urinary adverse effects (2,10). As long-term survival rates increase, providers need to gain a better understanding of the long-term impact of survivorship on patients and healthcare systems (11,12). Few studies review the general prevalence and range of such complications, while most investigate only specific complications (13–15). This study contributes to filling gaps in the understanding of cervical cancer survivorship by providing an overview of cervical cancer complications. It gives a clearer overview of how complications vary by treatment type, and time after treatment. By analysing these patterns, we aim to help provide information that can be used to guide improvements in care and support for survivors.

2. Methods

This study involved a narrative literature review exploring the challenges cervical cancer survivors faced after treatment. Academic databases Google Scholar and PubMed were used to gather relevant studies. The search focused on peer-reviewed articles published between 2008 and 2024 that examined physical, emotional, and social post-treatment complications. The primary keywords included “cervical cancer survivors,” “post-treatment complications,” “long-term effects,” and “survivorship.” The search strategy was: (“cervical cancer survivors” AND “post-treatment complications”) AND (“long-term effects” OR “quality of life”) AND (“developing countries” OR “low- and middle-income”) AND (“quality of life” OR “survivorship”). Studies focusing on other types of cancer were excluded. The selection process included title and abstract screening, and full-text reviews and categorization were conducted.

3. Analysis

Data from selected studies were extracted into an Excel sheet, categorizing key details such as complication types, regional differences, and treatment methods. Information such as authors, year, study method, design, population, and key findings were also recorded. The data were then analyzed to identify common patterns and inequalities, with a focus on trends in post-treatment complications among cervical cancer survivors. A thematic approach was used to organize the findings, allowing for a clear comparison of physical, emotional, and social impacts across survivor groups.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Characteristics and Summary of included studies

A total of 17 studies were included in this review among them, quantitative (n=1), mixed methods(n=1), systematic reviews (n=5), retrospective (n=5), including case-control (n=1), cross-sectional observational (n=1), chart review (n=1), review (n=1), retrospective (n=1); review (n=2),

cross-sectional survey-based (n=2), and worldwide analysis (n=1). The studies were conducted across multiple countries, USA (n=5): mixed(n=1), worldwide analysis(n=1), retrospective(n=1), retrospective review(n=1), retrospective chart review(n=1); Spain (n=3): worldwide analysis(n=1), retrospective case-control (n=1), systematic review(n=1); Italy (n=3): systematic review(n=2), quantitative (n=1); South Africa (n=2): systematic reviews (n=1), review (n=1); China (n=2): systematic review(n=1), cross-sectional survey-based (n=1); and from the Australia, UK, Russia, Sweden, France, Belgium, the Philippines, Japan, India, and Romania (n=1) each respectively. (Table 1). The sample sizes varied significantly based on study type and research focus. Systematic reviews ranged from 1356 to 10,847 participants and focused primarily on post-surgical morbidity, quality of life (QoL), and sexual dysfunction in cervical cancer survivors (16–20). Retrospective studies including case control and cross-sectional observational studies ranged from 25 to 693 participants. These studies were conducted in university medical centers, and teaching hospitals in the USA (12,21), aimed at the survivorship burden, treatment outcomes, clinicopathological factors linked to surgical complications, and quality of life (QoL) (12,15,21–23). The review studies examined the current cervical cancer treatments and the impact of treatment advancements on survivorship (7,9). The mixed-methods study and cross-sectional survey-based studies reviewed long-term survivorship issues, while the quantitative study investigated QoL issues and emotional distress (11,25,27).

Table 1

Table 1: Characteristics of included studies

No	First Author/Year	Title	Country	Study Type/Design	Aim	Setting/Population	Sample size	Main findings
1	Allanson, E. 2019	Morbidity after surgical management of cervical cancer in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis.	Australia, South Africa	Systematic review and meta-analysis	To investigate postsurgical morbidity in cervical cancer patients in LMICs.	11 middle-income countries	46 studies -N= 10,847 patients.	High surgical morbidity rates in CC patients in LMICs were observed, including blood transfusion (29%) and infection (8%), highlighting data limitations.
2	Van Kol, K. 2021	Adjuvant Hysterectomy for Cervical Cancer Patients Treated with Chemoradiation Therapy: A Systematic Review on the Pathology-Proven Residual Disease Rate	Netherlands	Systematic review	To determine the percentage of residual disease in adjuvant hysterectomy specimens.	Cervical cancer patients treated with chemoradiation therapy and adjuvant hysterectomy.	11 studies -N= 2077 patients	No association was found between chemoradiation therapy timing and residual disease in adjuvant hysterectomy specimens. Survival rates postchemoradiation and hysterectomy are low, with a high risk of complications after hysterectomy.

3	Ye, S. 2014	A systematic review of quality of life and sexual function of patients with cervical cancer after treatment	China	Systematic review	Summarize research on QoL and sexual function in cervical cancer survivors using selfreported data.	Studies from electronic database between May 1966 and May 2013.	N=32 studies	QoL and sexual function in CCSs were compromised compared to the general population to different extents.
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4	Cianci, S. 2023	Post Treatment Sexual Function and Quality of Life of Patients Affected by Cervical Cancer: A Systematic Review	Italy	Systematic review	Analyze scientific evidence on QoL and sexual function after surgical and adjuvant treatments.	Reported studies were published between 2003 and 2022(locations not mentioned)	N= 18 studies	Sexual dysfunction after CC treatment has a multifactorial etiology, negatively impacting QoL.
5	Tramacere, F. 2022	Assessment of Sexual Dysfunction in Cervical Cancer Patients after Different Treatment Modality: A Systematic Review	Italy and Spain	Systematic review	To evaluate sexual dysfunction in cervical cancer patients undergoing different treatment.	Included studies published from 2016 to 2022	N= 1356 patients	Physical, physiological, and social factors impact sexual function. Cervical cancer survivors treated with radiation have lower sexual and vaginal function than the general population.

6	MembrillaBeltran, L. 2023	Impact of Cervical Cancer on Quality of Life and Sexuality in Female Survivors	Spain	Retrospective case-control study	Examine QoL, sexual function, and satisfaction in Spanish cervical cancer survivors.	CC survivors in a Spanish population.	N= 66 patients	Cervical cancer survivors experience dysfunction, sexual dissatisfaction, and lower quality of life compared to healthy women.
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7	Stanca, M. 2022	The Overall Quality of Life and Oncological Outcomes Following Radical Hysterectomy in Cervical Cancer Survivors Results from a Large Long-Term Single-Institution Study	Romania	Retrospective cross-sectional observational study	Assess overall survival (OS) and QoL in cervical cancer survivors.	Patients who underwent RH at the First Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinic of Târgu Mureș, Romania, from January 2010 to March 2019.	N= 430 patients	Despite good OS, cervical cancer survivors have modest QoL and sexual function.
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8	Peerenboom, R. 2024	The burden of cervical cancer survivorship: Understanding morbidity and survivorship needs through hospital admissions.	United States	Retrospective chart review	To describe survivorship burden and risk factors for hospital admissions posttreatment	Patients treated for cervical cancer from 2014 to 2020 at a single urban academic institution.	N=366 patients	Cervical cancer survivors are a high-risk group often hospitalized after initial treatment.
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9	Khulpateea, B. 2020	Stage IVA cervical cancer: outcomes of disease-related complications and treatment	United States	A single institution retrospective review	To report treatment outcomes of stage IVA cervical cancer patients at a safety-net hospital.	Patients treated for stage IVA cervical cancer between January 2008 and July 2017 at Southwestern Medical Center at Dallas, Dallas, Texas, USA.	N= 25 patients	Fistula rate in stage IVA cervical cancer was 44%, mainly affecting gastrointestinal, urinary, and genital tracts. 111 unplanned admissions occurred in 25 patients.
10	Machida, H. 2019	Profile of treatment-related complications in women with clinical stage IB-IIB cervical cancer: A nationwide cohort study in Japan	Japan and USA	Retrospective study	Examine clinicopathological factors linked to surgical complications in stage IB-IIB cervical cancer.	Conducted at 87 institutions affiliated with the Japanese Gynecologic Oncology Group (JGOG)	N=693 women	Radiotherapy increased grade 3– 4 adverse events, while chemotherapy increased bladder dysfunction after radical hysterectomy for stage IB-IIB cervical cancer.
11	Burmeister, C. 2022	Cervical cancer therapies: Current challenges and future perspectives	South Africa	Review	Examine cervical cancer progression, current therapies, and emerging treatments.	Cervical cancer in various global contexts,	Multiple studies were reviewed	Current treatment options include surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, but they are often unaffordable and inaccessible in LMICs

12	Sri, U. N. S., 2024	A Comprehensive Exploration of Advances in Cervical Cancer Treatment: Targeted Therapy, Radiotherapy and Chemotherapy	India	Review	To provide an overview of cervical cancer, including its epidemiology, risk factors, and advancements in prevention and treatment.	Women diagnosed with cervical cancer (locations not mentioned)	Multiple studies were reviewed	External beam radiation alone is less effective than combined radiotherapy in treating cervical cancer.
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13	Sorokin, P. 2024	Impact of Various Treatment Modalities on Long-Term Quality of Life in Cervical Cancer Survivors	Russia	Cross-sectional survey-based study	Evaluate long-term QoL in cervical cancer survivors treated with various approaches.	Participants were women over 18, diagnosed with stage IA2-IIB cervical cancer, and who completed their treatment.	N= 173 patients	Cervical cancer survivors who had surgery alone reported the highest QoL and lower symptom intensity compared to those treated with RT or combinations.
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14	Zhou, W. 2016	Survey of cervical cancer survivors regarding quality of life and sexual function	China	Cross-sectional survey	To investigate the quality of life (QOL) of cervical cancer survivors in China.	Cervical cancer survivors were selected from 4 Tertiary Provincial Hospitals in Changsha, Hunan Province.	N= 140 patients	The quality of life and sexual function of cervical cancer survivors were notably low.
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15	Ferrandina, G. 2012	Quality of life and emotional distress in early stage and locally advanced cervical cancer patients: A prospective, longitudinal study	Italy	A prospective, longitudinal study this is quantitative	Investigate QoL issues and emotional distress across different treatment modalities.	Patients diagnosed with early-stage (ECC) or locally advanced cervical cancer (LACC) in Italy, able to read and understand Italian, in a clinical or hospital setting.	N= 227 patients	Lymphedema and menopausal symptoms were the most disabling treatment-related sequelae.
16	Arbyn, M. 2020	Estimates of incidence and mortality of cervical cancer in 2018: a worldwide analysis	Belgium, France, Spain, USA	A worldwide analysis	To assess cervical cancer burden as a baseline for WHO's elimination initiative	Analyzed data from 185 countries worldwide	Global Cancer Observatory 2018 database was used to estimate the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer.	CC remains a significant public health issue, particularly affecting middle-aged women in lessresourced countries.

17	Pfaendler, K. 2015	Cervical cancer survivorship: Long-term quality of life and social support.	USA	Mixed Methods – review & qualitative study	Review QoL in long-term cervical cancer survivors (≥5 years) and identified challenges.	Included studies were published from 1993-2014.	421 patients in Taiwan, 291 survivors in the Netherlands, 346 patients across 12 countries, and unspecified in other countries.	Patients undergoing radical surgery and radiotherapy experience greater persistent bladder, bowel, and sexual dysfunction long after treatment.
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4.2 Post-Treatment Complications in Cervical Cancer Survivors

Cervical cancer survivors experience a high risk of complications following treatment (15,24). Many patients are re-hospitalized after completing their primary treatment (12,21), with one study reporting that 43% of cervical cancer survivors were admitted to the hospital following the completion of the initial round of treatment (12). Several studies have highlighted physical, emotional and social complications among cervical cancer survivors (11,12,19). The most common complications among cervical cancer survivors include pain, fatigue, insomnia, and appetite loss as major physical symptoms (22,25). Additionally, complications such as fistula formation, percutaneous nephrostomy-related issues, and chronic pain require intensive supportive care (11,21). In a study by Pfaendler et. al. 2015 approximately 20% of cervical cancer survivors developed chronic bladder dysfunction and psychosocial issues impacting the quality of life including mood disorders, stress, body image concerns, and fear of recurrence (11,12). Another study reported that 35% of patients experienced complications related to adjuvant hysterectomy after chemoradiation therapy, which had an overall fistula rate of 5% (19). While the prevalence of post-treatment problems is generally comparable between LMICs and HICs, certain events, such as fistula formation (1.2% ureterovaginal, 2.8% vesicovaginal) and pulmonary embolism (2.8%), appear to be recorded at lower rates in HICs (20).

4.3 Physical Complications

Due to the nature of cervical cancer and its treatment, patients experience physical complications. Patients undergoing neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NACT), radical hysterectomy, radiotherapy, or surgery frequently experience sexual dysfunction, such as sexual discomfort, pain during intercourse, vaginal dryness, decreased sexual desire, lack of arousal and orgasm, decreased lubrication and sensation, vaginal atrophy, fibrosis, strictures, stenosis, and cystitis sexual discomfort, and sexual dissatisfaction (11,12,16,18,22,23,27), which can lead to dyspareunia and

decreased sexual satisfaction (18,22). These complications can be categorized into short-term and long-term effects. Short-term complications include blood transfusions, infections, ureteric and nerve injuries, and menopausal symptoms (20,23). Long-term effects include chronic pain, fistula formation, persistent bladder, bowel, menopausal symptoms, and sexual dysfunction (11,20,22). Radiotherapy has been linked to fatigue, dyspnoea, loss of appetite, menopausal symptoms, and sexual dysfunction than radical surgery (11,17,25,26,27), highlighting the importance of tailored treatment options for improving long-term survivability results (25,26). While neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NACT) followed by surgery and chemoradiation therapy have good five-year survival rates (72-76%), quality of life remains a major problem, particularly for young survivors with a long-life expectancy (23,25). Blood transfusion (29%), nerve injury (1%), bladder injury (1%), ureteric injury (1%), vascular injury (2%), and fistula development (2%) are the most common surgical complications recorded (20). Survivors may also have lymphoedema, ureteral strictures, flank discomfort, pelvic or lower back pain, and lower limb oedema (7,26).

4.4 Psychological and Social Complications

Cervical cancer survivors often also face psychosocial challenges, including anxiety, depression, social isolation, distress in the family, roles and relationships, lack of interest in sex, and fear of recurrence, which negatively impact their quality of life (11,16,17,22,27). Short-term psychological issues include acute stress disorder (30%) and post-traumatic stress disorder (41%) within three months of treatment (11). These psychological impacts are often caused by the physical effects of treatment, including sexual dysfunction, and urinary incontinence, which can be both a physical and emotional burden (11,16,22,27). While long-term effects involve psychological discomfort (11,22,26). Radiotherapy has been linked to higher rates of somatization, insomnia, and depression, than radical surgery (25,26,27). Financial issues, poor body image, and sexual inactivity are all related to increased anxiety and lower existential well-being among

survivors (16,17). Patients who undergo chemoradiotherapy have a lower quality of life and higher depression levels than those receiving radiotherapy alone (26). Social support is essential for coping with the cancer diagnosis, treatment, and the emotional consequences thereafter (11,16).

4.5 Differences in Post-Treatment Complications between High-Income and Low- and Middle-Income Countries

Cervical cancer is a major global burden, particularly in low-income countries (LMICs) where resources are limited, indicating that survivors in these areas may face more serious difficulties than those in high-income nations (7). Cervical cancer remained the primary cause of cancer-related mortality among women in 42 low-income countries (14). The overall five-year survival rate in LMICs is around 50%, which is much lower than the 80% reported in high-income countries (HICs) (20). This could be related to later-stage diagnoses, limited access to adjuvant therapy, and a higher rate of HIV infection among younger women (20,23).

4.6 Impact of Treatment Modalities on Post-Treatment Complications

The options for cervical cancer treatment depend on the stage of cancer and the patient's needs and include surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, or a combination of these types of treatments (7,9). The long-term quality of life (QoL) of cervical cancer survivors is strongly connected to treatment modalities, with patients undergoing extensive surgery and radiotherapy experiencing persistent bladder, bowel, and sexual dysfunction (11,16,17,27). Adjuvant hysterectomy after chemoradiation is related to major complication risks, such as increased fistula formation and poor tissue repair, which can further impact overall health (19,25). Radiotherapy is related with persistent fatigue, insomnia, dyspnoea, and loss of appetite all of which have a major impact on the patient's lives (11,17,25). Patients treated with radiotherapy alone or in combination with

other therapies frequently report lower outcomes than those treated with surgery alone, despite developments in surgical procedures improving outcomes for intermediate and high-risk cases (17,25). Younger cervical cancer patients, particularly those who are socially and sexually active, have major long-term challenges as a result of cancer therapy (23). Socially and sexually active youngwomen with cervical cancer face risks to their lives due to treatments such as surgery, radiotherapy (RT), chemotherapy (CT), or a combination (23,25). While survival rates are high, long-term QoL remains a significant concern, particularly for young survivors with a long-life expectancy, as they may experience persistent side effects from treatment (23,25).

5.1. Discussion

A key finding of this literature review is the variation in post-treatment complications based on treatment modality. It shows that while chemotherapy and surgery caused persistent pain, nerve damage, and sexual dysfunction (7,11,17), radiotherapy is highly related to bladder and bowel dysfunction (11,17,25). Additionally, psychosocial challenges, including anxiety, depression, and body image concerns, are frequently reported, with survivors in LMICs often experiencing a greater emotional and financial burden due to limited healthcare infrastructure (16,18). The strengths of this study include a comprehensive analysis of physical difficulties, treatment across different treatment modalities, as well as time after treatment. Our findings add to the existing research by showing various post-treatment consequences and psychosocial challenges that cervical cancer survivors deal with (10,13,28). Many studies focus on physical health issues (28,29), such as sexual dysfunction bowel and bladder dysfunction (18,29), as well as the long-term effects of treatments including surgery, radiation, and chemotherapy (10,28). All of which are important for managing cervical cancer patients. However, these studies did not focus much on the emotional, social, and mental challenges that survivors face. Some studies indicate that survivors experience mental health issues, and financial difficulties (13,29). In addition, majority

of the studies were conducted in high-income countries, leaving knowledge gaps for lower- and middle-income countries, where cervical cancer is more common (1,4,5). Future research should focus on standardizing post-treatment outcomes when selecting treatment modalities for cervical cancer patients, expanding survivorship programs in LMICs, and developing interventions to mitigate long-term complications.

5.2 Limitations of the study

This research has a number of limitations. First, information on problems after treatment might be underreported in low-income nations or regions. Secondly the sample size imprecision, makes it difficult to obtain enough relevant data because the studies were based on existing studies. Furthermore, the inability to interview survivors limited the range of information that could be collected.

5.3. Conclusions

This literature review underscores that sexual dysfunction is one of the major challenges that cervical cancer survivors face, which persists long after curative treatment. The long-term physical, emotional, and social challenges worsen the overall quality of life, with treatment type playing a crucial role in determining the severity of complications. Survivors in low- and middle-income countries had worse outcomes emphasizing the urgent need for improved survivorship care, emotional support, and treatment access globally.

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